

World Digital School Project

Applied Better Practice Brief:

Improving Cybersecurity with Simulated Phishing Exercises

One of the biggest cybersecurity threats facing international schools is Business Email Compromise, or BEC for short. BEC is a form of cybercrime where attackers use email to trick employees into transferring money or sharing sensitive information. We can make our systems secure and prevent intrusions to our networks, but when criminals use social engineering to exploit trust, the vulnerabilities are with the humans at our school, and not our technical systems. Schools whose systems are compromised in this sort of attack can suffer from huge financial losses and damages to their reputations.

Schools can help prevent BEC by training employees to recognize common techniques and lures and encourage them to report suspected fraud. Many international schools are conducting simulated phishing attacks in order to provide this training.

GETTING LEADERSHIP BUY-IN BY COLLECTING EXAMPLES

It's important that your school's leadership understand the need to conduct training and support the time and money that need to be spent. At your regional meetings or job-alikes, take some time to share "horror stories" of recent cyberattacks. By telling your stories and sharing what you've learned, you can help others. Here are three types of attacks you'll probably hear about:

Invoice Fraud: One of your school's vendors sends the accounting department an invoice with new bank details. Upon careful inspection, it turns out that the invoice is fraudulent. Attackers sometimes create new email domains that are very similar to the company they are impersonating. They may gain access to an actual account at the company and use this account to send their fake invoice. Make sure that your accounting department is alert anytime a vendor changes their banking details.

Head-of-School Impersonation Fraud: A number of teachers or employees get a message from someone who appears to be the head of school. Since their name and photo is usually on the school's website, it's easy for a criminal to create a free email address and impersonate them. They may ask for urgent wire transfers, donations, or gift cards. Any urgent request for money should be seen as a trigger for extra careful inspection.

Account Compromise: The worst form of invoice fraud to hit a school is when your school's parents are sent fraudulent tuition invoices. Criminals can spend time researching your parent community and learning what your invoices and letterhead look like. This job is easy for them if they compromise one of your school's email accounts - especially one with access to accounting or tuition information. They might carefully time their attack to happen on a holiday when the leadership team is unable to respond quickly to parent concerns. In addition to the financial cost of an attack like this, a school's reputation and relationship with parents and the community can be seriously damaged.

Ransomware: A ransomware attack on a school's computer system can be initiated when an employee clicks on a malicious link in an email. In a less severe attack, only one computer is encrypted, and the hackers demand payment to restore the files. If the files are backed up to cloud storage, the loss is limited to the single computer.

However, a more serious attack occurs when personally identifiable and sensitive information about students and families is stolen and published online. The attackers then demand a ransom from the school to prevent further sharing of the information. Regardless of whether the school pays the ransom, the attackers may also contact students and parents directly and demand payment from them.

TRAINING THROUGH SIMULATED PHISHING ATTACKS

You can measure how likely your users are to fall for one of these attacks by sending a simulated phishing email. Many vendors will help you conduct a phishing campaign. They'll use common techniques and lures to convince your employees to click a suspicious link, then provide you with detailed analytics to help you learn who on your staff is the most phish-prone. These simulations can expose the weaknesses in staff behavior and allow you to proactively train your most susceptible employees before a true problem surfaces.

Here are some tips to make your phish-training campaign a success:

- **Establish a baseline.** Before you announce your training campaign, conduct an unannounced test to gauge which users are prone to clicking suspicious links before their training has begun. This data is helpful later when measuring success, and can also help get leadership buy-in.
- **Use realistic scenarios.** An off-the-shelf phishing simulation test might use messages that won't make sense in your context - like an announcement from an American driver's license bureau. Keep the simulations fresh and unpredictable.
- **Provide timely feedback.** Offer immediate guidance to employees who fail the simulation. Even if your chosen software solution has this feature built in, an in-person visit can help reassure them that the link was just a test. You can show them what elements of the email you would have found suspicious and build in some just-in-time training while remaining empathetic.
- **Communicate clearly.** Be aware that some employees may feel violated or lied to after the baseline test. Make sure that your communication about the training campaign takes these feelings into consideration and conveys the serious need for improving security.
- **Start with easier scenarios.** Gradually increase the difficulty of the simulations over time.
- **Repeat regularly.** Conducting simulations on a regular basis will help reinforce good security habits.
- **Focus on education.** Emphasize learning and improvement so that the training doesn't feel like a punishment or a "gotcha."

CASE STUDIES

These examples are not endorsements. The World Digital School Project does not recommend any vendors over others. These case studies were gathered through online forums by members of the WDSP, who conducted interviews with technology leaders to learn their opinions.

InfoSec

InfoSec IQ offers a comprehensive solution that includes phishing simulations, a tool for consistently reporting phishing, training and awareness programs, and data dashboards. Phishing simulations provide immediate feedback for users, and those who are "phished" can be assigned additional training to enhance their awareness. The PhishNotify tool can also be embedded into Gmail, allowing users to easily and consistently report phishing emails, whether they are part of a simulation or not.

The security awareness training includes printable posters, infographics, brief animated training videos in multiple languages, and assessments. The program is structured with detailed "Program Kits" that cover a broad range of cybersecurity topics beyond phishing detection. Both the training and "Program Kits" are customizable, engaging, and varied to meet the specific needs of your organization, ensuring relevance and effectiveness.

Phishing simulations and training campaigns are further enhanced by insightful data dashboards, which provide performance metrics and help identify areas for improvement. Charlotte Diller from the International School of Kuala Lumpur shares that she is highly satisfied with the setup, support, quality, ease of use, and cost.

KnowBe4

KnowBe4 has a large library of training videos, which allows technology leaders to customize the type of training their users need. Mike Keweler of the German European School Singapore put together a 35-minute collection of training videos for his senior leadership team that one member of the team called the most interesting cyber security training they had ever had. The training programs are customizable, so after a simulated phishing campaign, people who click on a suspicious link can be assigned to mandatory training. Keweler requires his phish-prone users to watch a five-minute video training playlist, after which they must pass a three-question quiz. He reports that he is impressed with the detailed analytics interface in KnowBe4.

A particularly useful feature of KnowBe4 is the ability for a school to upload additional training materials. Schools can use the awareness training and analytics features in KnowBe4 to conduct mandatory training in a variety of areas besides cybersecurity. For example, Luis Olarte at Colegio Nueva Granada in Bogotá uses KnowBe4 for training in child protection, health and safety and local legal compliance with data privacy regulations.

CyberNut

Kevin Crouch at Western Academy of Beijing has used both KnowBe4 and Cybernut. While he was impressed with the maturity and feature set of the KnowBe4 platform, he likes the simplicity of CyberNut. He reports that users at his school enjoy the gamification that CyberNut embeds in their training, which make them feel both educational and fun, compared with his previous KnowBe4 campaigns, which were seen as a “gotcha.” While most companies providing simulated phishing training are aimed at corporate users, CyberNut is specifically targeting the K-12 marketplace with pricing that is designed to make it affordable enough to include students in the list of users who are trained. While it’s unlikely that compromised student emails will pose as great a threat to your school as an attack on the accounting office, helping students stay safe online is surely aligned with all of our technology strategies.

CyberNut is also used at The American School in Japan, who report that they are very happy with the proactive account management team at CyberNut as well as the responsiveness of their tech support department. Dion Norman at Chadwick International in Korea, said that he appreciates Cybernut’s gamified approach and the informative new dashboard that offers useful insights into user engagement

Some schools use multiple platforms. Nate Doelling at Seoul Foreign School uses KnowBe4 for training teachers and CyberNut for students.

REPORTING TOOLS

Most of these tools allow the inclusion of a report button directly in the email platform, giving teachers and other employees the ability to easily report a suspicious email. Users will need training in how to use this button, and will also need to be reminded that forwarding malicious emails is unsafe practice. The reporting button should disable the malicious links and allow the schools technology help desk to investigate the issue safely. Ideally, your school’s ticketing system can help you monitor and respond to threats and provide one-on-one support to people who may need help identifying suspicious emails or mitigating damage caused by clicking on malicious links.

FIVE SIMPLE NEXT STEPS FOR BETTER PRACTICE

- **Conduct a baseline assessment** of how phish-prone your faculty and staff are by engaging in a simulated phishing attack.
- **Communicate quickly** with everyone who received the simulation. Make sure they understand the seriousness of the threat and reassure them that the links they may have clicked on were just a simulation.
- **Report the results** to the school's leadership team or school board. Use the results to justify additional training or investment in cybersecurity solutions.
- **Group your faculty and staff into clusters based on risk level.** For example, users like accounting staff with access to financial information might need more frequent assessment through follow-up phishing simulations. Users who repeatedly click on simulated phishing links might need in-person training.
- **Gamify the results**, providing prizes or other incentives to employees who correctly report the simulations.

IN CONCLUSION

Business Email Compromise can result in significant financial losses, reputational damage, and legal consequences for international schools. Conducting simulated phishing exercises can help you evaluate and mitigate your risk from such an incident.

Keep in mind that the sophistication of these attacks will only increase as cybercriminals gain access to more advanced AI software and automated agents. By raising awareness now, you decrease the chance of employees falling for real phishing attacks as they become more prevalent.

About the World Digital School Project

The WDSP, formerly the World Virtual School Project, is an initiative focused on leveraging digital systems to ensure safety, security, and innovation for learning in international schools. This brief was collaboratively written by:

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